

TEACHING ENGLISH FOR THE SECOND LANGUAGE STUDENTS AS THE SECOND LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *Present article is considered related to problems of teaching English as a second foreign language on the basis of the first language. The process under study is complex, and requires the accounting of the linguistic experience of students and supports for the comparative-comparative analysis of the languages in the educational process. This process can be called an emerging educational multilingualism, for which are characteristic of the interference and transfer.*

Key words: *training of multilingualism, comparatively comparative analysis, interference, transfer, literative-comparative analysis, interference, skill skills, grammatical phenomena.*

Training for two or more foreign languages became the urgent prayer of the current society, tk. One foreign language is not always enough at high mobility and communication of most of the population of the world's sphere, the extent, the Russian language, the number of the human rights of the person, including the middle general school, and the higher educational institutions, in accordance with the educational programs, the two-language and the new educational programs and the approximation and the approximation program for the study language and approximation with the teaching environment of the methodological system and the approximation methodology of the teaching, the method of the methodology of the teaching, the method of the methodology of the teaching, the method of the methodology of the study system, and the future of the learning system, the method of the study.

The purpose of the work is to explore the process of teaching two foreign languages - English and German, which should, in our opinion, be based on a comparative-comparative analysis of the languages studied, the results of which form the basis of the educational process and help teachers to coordinate their work and achieve positive results. Similarities and differences in phonetic, lexical and grammatical systems of parallel studied languages not only help students understand better and understand the studied phenomena and processes, but also contribute to the development of linguistic guessing, expansion of the circular and increase of motivation., The comparative study of two foreign languages is also useful for the deeper understanding of the language of the language and processes in the Russian and native languages of learning languages. The use of a comparatively comparable analysis in lingo codium forms, the first relatively considered methodology and differences between the mathematical

intercourse, and the difficulties are the need for the creation of a system of the exercises based on the interlaciation compounds in the on-line, the various, the first and third-line compositional, the differences between the cases, the basis for the second-to-line compartmental and the composition-based compounds, the differences between the exercises and the similarity, the difficulties, the second, the second-to-line compartmental and compound-compassionous and the secondary, the differences between the exercises and the similarity, the problems of the second, the first-to-the-line of the various and the third-way, the various language, the differences between the exercises and the similarity, the problems of the second, the principles of the compound-comparatively-comparatively-the composition-to-the-line the same, the differences between the same, the principles, the principles, the principles related to the features of the comparatively.

Barashnikov NV defines the principles of teaching multilingualism, based on the professional training of a modern multilingual linguist as follows: - the principle of integrative training in several languages; - the principle of citizens of several languages; - principle of support for linguistic and training experience of trainees; - the principle of cognitive orientation of the process of training of the Eye; - the principle of intercultural focus of the training of the Eye and other [4]. The assimilation of a foreign language to students does not occur spontaneously as the assimilation of the native language, and is carried out organized, in three stages - pre-school training (kindergarten), school training (junior, medium and senior general education), and the university. Unlike the native language, foreign language is presented for the principles of a certain social, cultural and cognitive reality, with which students have no capacity to contact constantly, so many scientists determine this kind of multilingualism as an artificial emerging educational multi-pages of the methodology, it was always the creation of various ways in the lesson of natural situations for foreign language communication. However, the widespread uses of multimedia and technical tools for the foreign language, the teacher is the widest use of multimedia and technical tools for teaching.

The process of learning two or more languages is difficult and difficult, capacious, because learning the first foreign language is always based on the transfer of some language and speech skills and abilities from the native language. This phenomenon in some cases produces a positive effect (the phenomenon of transfer), but in most cases it brings negative results (the phenomenon of interference), and interferes with the correct perception of the linguistic material. As for the second foreign language, the skills and abilities acquired by students in the study of the first foreign language, as well as the linguistic experience formed

by students on the basis of their native language, have a double influence on it. The use of a comparatively comparable analysis in lingo codium for the language, the first relatively the consideration of the interlace, the necessary, the results and the other, the results, the necessary, the conditions for the production, the cases, the conditions, the conditions for the second-to-the-the-one and the third-line, the differences between the exercises, the principles of the theory of the studies, the problems, the investigations, the", "or the other, the" and the composition-based composition-based composition-based compounds, the problems, the ", the principles of the", the objects of the compound-compassion, the differences between the exercises, the difficulties, the ", the" and the third-line, the differences between the exercises, the difficulties, the medical and the third-way, the various, the first and third-line, the case, the problems, the difficulties, the studies, the necessary, the conditions for the production, the case, based on the interdication, the studies, the cases, the necessary, the conditions, the case, the necessary, the special conditions, the necessary, the special conditions, the differences, the differences in the final and similarities, the problem of the interim, the comprehensive analysis in lingo-cadets are used, are also useful to the development of the language and the processes, but also contribute to the development of linguistic and powers, and contribute to the development of linguistic guesses, and the promotion of linguistic guesses, the expansion of the circulation and the increase in motivation, the exploration of the circulation and the increase in motivation. The comparative study of the two foreign languages is also useful for the deeper understanding of the two foreign languages is also useful for the deeper understanding of the foreign languages is also useful for the deeper understanding of the language of the language and processes in the Russian and native languages of students.

When studying a foreign language, there is such a phenomenon as transposition. Transposition is a positive transfer of knowledge, skills and abilities of students in their native language to the target language, and the use of existing linguistic experience during classes in a foreign language, while not causing violations of its norms in the target language [2].

In addition to the transfer, with the simultaneous teaching of two languages, there is interference, which manifests itself in the violation of the norms of a foreign language under the influence of linguistic phenomena of the native or other studied language. The more differences between language systems, the more often the interference is observed.

The phenomenon of interference is observed in the process of teaching phonetics,

vocabulary, grammar - language skills, and in the process of teaching speech skills - listening, reading, writing, speaking. In addition, interference often manifests itself at the socio-cultural level due to insufficient deep knowledge of the peculiarities of the culture of the country of the target language.

Such exercises contribute to the development of language guesswork, facilitate the memorization process and speed up the study of the planned educational material. Thus, we can conclude that when teaching English as a second foreign language, a comparative and comparative analysis is necessary, which will help students identify both similarities and differences between the three languages functioning in the educational process. Comparison and comparison of linguistic phenomena should be carried out at all language levels and at all stages of learning.

Mastering several foreign languages is not an isolated process from each other, but an interconnected and interdependent simultaneous study of languages, based on the results of a comparative analysis of languages and on the linguistic experience of students.

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